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TiO₂/polymeric supported silver nanoparticles applied as superior nanocatalyst in reduction reactions

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Abstract

Anovel polymeric nanocomposites (TiO₂/poly(acrylamide-co-methylenbisacrylamide)) decorated with silver nanoparticles (Ag NPs) denoted as (Ag–TiO₂/poly(AM-co-MBAM)) was prepared and fully characterized. Initially, the surface of TiO₂ nanoparticles was modified using methacryloxypropyltrimethoxysilan (MAPTMS), thus a C[dbnd]C bond for polymerization was generated, which polymerized with acrylamide and methylenbisacrylamide monomers. Ag NPs then were immobilized on the surface of this obtained polymeric nanocomposites via reduction in the presence of AgNO₃. The catalytic efficiency of Ag–TiO₂/poly(AM-co-MBAM) nanocomposites was investigated for the reduction of nitroarenes and some carbonyl compounds in the presence of sodium borohydride (NaBH₄) as reducing agent in aqueous media to give the corresponding anilines and alcohols with excellent yields and short reaction times, respectively. The nanocatalyst was easily recovered and reused for at least seven cycles without appreciable loss of its catalytic activity.

Keywords: Carbonyl compounds, Nitroarenes, Reduction, Silver nanoparticles, Surface modification, TiO₂, nanocomposites, Acrylic monomers, Amides, Carbonyl compounds, Catalyst activity, Metal nanoparticles, Nanocomposites, Silver Nanoparticles, Surface treatment, Titanium dioxide, Catalytic efficiencies, Polymeric nanocomposites, Reduction of nitroarenes, Short reaction time, nanoparticles (AgNps), Sodium boro hydrides